

DEVELOPMENT OF TYPES OF SPEECH ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the development of types of speech activity of students in Russian language classes. It is noted that in modern university education, a special place among the disciplines that are a compulsory educational component is occupied by the Russian language for undergraduate studies. And the main task of the discipline is to make learning not only effective, but also interesting, in order to involve students in the learning process, making them the main and active participants.

In modern society, there is a tendency to strengthen the role of a foreign language in all spheres of human life, which requires a new approach to teaching foreign languages, the essence of which lies not only in the methodology of teaching certain linguistic aspects, but also in the formation of a new worldview.

Modern social development under the influence of the scientific and technological revolution strengthens social needs for interlingual communication and stimulates the need to master foreign languages as a means of communication.

Learning a foreign language is designed to form a personality capable and willing to participate in intercultural communication. The focus of our attention is on the means of developing speech skills in Russian language classes. However, at present we can state a decrease in students' motivation to learn a foreign language. That is why the formation of positive motivation should be considered by the teacher as a special task. As a rule, motives are associated with the cognitive interests of students, the need to master new knowledge, skills, and abilities. But the first and natural need of students when learning the Russian language is communication. To organize a favorable climate that orients students toward communication, it is necessary to choose forms of classes that will stimulate their activities.

In various works on the theory, methods of teaching and education, methodological researchers give different interpretations of the linguodidactic foundations for the formation of speech skills in Russian language classes. There are many problems and shortcomings in this matter. Speech activity is one of the types of human activity, understood by methodologists as “an active, purposeful, mediated by the language system and conditioned by the communication situation, the process of transmitting and receiving a message.”

So, first, let’s try to define the word “speaking.” There are many definitions, and all of them are considered correct and appropriate.

Speaking is a type of speech activity that is realized when the need for verbal influence on the interlocutor arises in the mind of the speaker. The speaking process is influenced by various factors, including: the purpose for which the speech act is performed; topic of communication; time and place of communication; relations between interlocutors (neutral, official, friendly, advice, agreement); the social and communicative role of partners (student and teacher, superior and subordinate, fellow students).

Work on teaching oral speech is based on the fact that real communication can be carried out in the form of dialogue and monologue.

According to Uzbek and Russian researchers and methodologists, teaching speaking includes three components:

- ✓ introduction of language material into the students’ memory;
- ✓ developing skills to operate with this material;
- ✓ development of skills in using speech for real communicative purposes.

Productive types of speech activity include speaking and writing, and receptive types include listening and reading. Speaking and writing play an active role in the communication process; they are aimed at generating speech, therefore they are classified as productive types of speech activity.

Listening and reading are a type of speech activity that is aimed at perception, reception of information and its subsequent processing, therefore they are classified as receptive types of speech activity.

Reading is a receptive type of speech activity, because it relies on the perception of graphic linguistic signs. Reading is not only perception, but also the process of extracting information. The importance of reading in a person's life is extremely great; it is through reading that we receive a large amount of information we need. Recently, the ability to read a foreign language has been considered important for a literate person. Reading develops memory and improves speech. In addition, through reading, students become acquainted with the countries of the language they are studying.

The German methodologist G. Pitho rightly noted that there is hardly a person who denies the great importance of citationality for teaching foreign language speech. A situation is a stimulus for speech and a set of events and relationships. The most common understanding of a situation is to understand it as a set of circumstances of reality, the background against which some events or actions unfold, and these circumstances should serve as a stimulus for speech action. Based on this, methodologists recommend making extensive use of visual aids to create situations.

In addition, as teaching practice shows, as a result of completing a system of exercises, students master the communicative ability to manage dialogic communication, which contributes to the development of students' initiative, as well as the development and improvement of oral speech skills.

According to K.S. Krichevskaya and M.A. Akhmedova, the inclusion of broadening their general horizons in the target setting of teaching Russian as a foreign language will also lead to increased interest in the language being studied and persistent motivation.

In the educational process, students master a wide variety of knowledge, skills and abilities. This forces the teacher to use an appropriate variety of methods. To assess knowledge, oral and written survey methods are most often used. Conversations, testing, questioning, and oral questioning are organized in such a way as to encourage either all those involved to respond - a frontal approach, or some of them - an individual approach. The use of modern technologies stimulated the creation by us, teachers, of the "Russian language textbook: development of oral speech skills of students studying at non-linguistic universities." The manual on the development of Russian speech pays attention to the formation of linguistic and cultural competence in classes in the discipline "Russian language". The methodology for teaching the Russian language is represented by thematic tasks, including texts, pre-text and post-text exercises and tasks focused on the study of language and culture.

Thus, the basic rules for the development of students' speech activity can be expressed in six words:

These words (and, of course, the memo) are a guide to creating your own statement and at the same time the key to reviewing a listened speech, a plan for its analysis.

So, the idea of students' speech development in the process of learning the Russian language is the most fruitful and is actively being developed in modern science. The achievements of psycholinguistics, functional grammar and other branches of linguistics create the prerequisites for the development of new approaches to teaching the Russian language and a new course with a pronounced speech focus. Over the past decade, a huge amount of experimental material has been accumulated and comprehended, defining the main directions, the implementation of which creates conditions for intensive speech development of students in the process of learning the Russian language.

The most complete implementation in the development of new content for teaching the Russian language is found in the idea of focusing the learning process on the development of the main types of speech activity in their unity and interconnection. Meanwhile, the main attention in Russian (non-native) language lessons is still mainly focused on the formation of written language skills, as evidenced, for example, by the nature of the tests in the subject, which are predominantly performed in written form. The system of tasks assessing reading and listening skills of texts with linguistic content is also not fully developed.

At the same time, research confirms the effectiveness of the teaching approach, in which increased attention is paid to reading, which ensures the development and improvement of other types of speech activity. Such work is built primarily on the basis of educational and scientific text with linguistic content. Currently, various forms of presenting such texts in textbooks and teaching aids are being developed, as well as various ways of organizing work with them, ensuring the full development of reading, listening, speaking and writing skills.

It is necessary to especially emphasize that this focus on teaching the Russian language has interdisciplinary significance and in the near future should be reflected in the documents regulating the work of a teacher at a university: in the standards for assessing knowledge, skills

and abilities in various subjects, as well as in documents defining the basic requirements a unified speech regime at the university.

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